

FEATURES OF FORMING STUDENTS INDEPENDENT WORK IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Traditionally, students' educational activities mean their work in the classroom. But educational activities include, in addition to classroom work, implementation of homework, independent work in the academic discipline and extracurricular work. At the same time, the independent work of students in the process of educational activities is the least studied and is of the greatest interest from the point of view of analysis. The student's personal qualities, such as self-organization, independence, self-control, are manifested precisely in independent work. And this student's work can be the basis for restructuring the student's own positions in the educational process.

Independence is defined as a personality quality, expressed in the ability to set certain goals for oneself and achieve them on one's own. Personal activity is a person's active attitude to the world, the ability to make socially significant transformations of the material and spiritual environment on the basis of mastering the socio-historical experience of mankind; manifests itself in creative activity, acts of will, and communication. Independent educational work should be perceived by students as a free choice activity, which will be accepted with their interests. As an activity, it consists of a number of actions: awareness of the purpose of one's activity, acceptance of a learning task, giving it personal meaning, subordination of other interests to the fulfillment of these tasks [1].

The quality of teaching and independent cognitive activity of students affects the effectiveness of learning. But independent work of students is the leading form of learning. It is impossible to impart knowledge unless students

make an effort to accept and internalize that knowledge. To assimilate knowledge firmly, it is necessary to listen, comprehend information and conduct analysis.

Another feature of a student's independent work is that in the process of mental work learner improves and develops as a person of high culture. Due to such independent work culture of mental work is developed. A person masters reading techniques, studies books, takes notes and develops needs for independent activity.

The educational process in a higher educational institution is significantly different from secondary school. There are no special tasks or day-to-day supervision at the university. Students have greater freedom to act and conduct independent work, and they give a report on their work almost only at the end of each semester, i.e. twice a year. Therefore, the transition period from school to university is often difficult. In reality, some students, by the time they pass course exams, receive admission, have accumulated a lot of unfinished work, for which, as a rule, there is no time left.

Therefore, studies at a higher educational institution should begin with systematic and daily work, proper distribution of time for independent work over months, weeks and days. The main condition for successful study at a university is uniform work throughout the semester. It is always necessary to remember that the student period of life is not only interesting lectures and classes, creative evenings and meetings, sports and amateur artistic activities, but also above all systematic, serious and complex independent work.

Our national education system is built on the principles of the humanistic direction in philosophy, psychology and pedagogy. The main distinctive feature of this direction in pedagogy is special attention to the individuality of the student, his or her personality, a clear focus on the conscious development of independent critical thinking, independent active cognitive activity of each student, taking into account his or her characteristics and capabilities. This approach is considered in world pedagogical practice as an alternative to the traditional one, based mainly on the student's assimilation of ready-made knowledge and its reproduction [2].

Correct and skillful organization of learning activities in the classroom is the basis for students' independent work. There is a transition from external control of the teacher to self-control of the student and from external assessment to the formation of his self-esteem. Thus, independent work of students is considered as work that they do without the direct participation of a teacher, but according to teacher's instructions. It is performed at a specially designated time. During independent work, students consciously achieve their goals in tasks, using efforts and achieving the results of their actions. During student' independent work the guidance of a teacher is necessary. The teacher needs to teach students a variety of methods and techniques for independent work, create tasks with a gradual increase in the degree of independence, instruct students, and teach them self-control.

Independent work of students at a university is an important type of educational and scientific activity of a student. Independent work of students plays a significant role in rating learning technology. The state standard provides, as a rule, 50% of the hours of the total labor intensity of the discipline for students' independent work. In this regard, studying at a university includes two parts that are almost identical in scope and mutual influence - the learning process and the self-study process. Therefore, independent work of learners should become effective and purposeful work for students [3].

Independent work in the learning process is necessary both for students' mastery of knowledge, skills and abilities, and for the development of cognitive abilities, the development of which is facilitated by the activities that students engage in in the classroom.

The volume of independent work and its differentiation according to the forms of training course, as well as the ratio between hours of classroom and independent work in each academic discipline, significantly depend on the pedagogical methodology used by a teacher and a type of, as well as the degree of use of modern information educational technologies. In addition, during the academic semester, the weekly amount of independent work does not changed. As more and more educational material is studied, independent work and classroom

work become approximately equal in volume, but already at the end of the semester, independent work can significantly exceed classroom work.

Any independent work of a student must correspond to the student's learning capabilities and satisfy the principle of gradual transition from one level of complexity to another. The main goal of independent work is not only to consolidate, expand and deepen the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities, but also to study and assimilate new material without help [4].

An effective stage in the implementation of independent work is a workshop, in which the teacher acts as a consultant and monitors the student's activities. In order to stimulate and constantly maintain students' interest in acquiring new knowledge, it is necessary to develop their self-education skills.

Students must master the basic and individual components of a teacher's work:

- work with scientific, methodological and educational literature;
- present educational material, create a system of differentiated exercises and manage it in problem solving process;
- use techniques for posing questions, formulating organizing and controlling questions;
- respond quickly and adequately to an emerging learning situation [5].

The core of independent work is a cognitive or problematic task that determines the entire its process.

Independent work of students is an obligatory component of educational activities; therefore, it requires careful methodological study and recommendations for its organization in faculties and departments. An analysis of methodological literature has shown that the problems of independent activity have been developed in theoretical terms quite deeply. However, the specifics of universities are different, so it is impossible to find the same solutions for each educational organization. One of the most important principles of modern university education is the ability to learn to acquire knowledge independently.

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